

Design and Evaluation of Herbal Lip Balm by using Beet Root

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Abstract:- Cosmetics are the substance used to alter the appearance or fragrances of the human body. Nowadays the demands for herbal cosmetics in the world market are growing and are inevitable gifts of nature. There is a wide range of herbal cosmetic products to satisfy the need of women. In contrast to synthetic ones, herbal cosmetics are safe for human health. Herbal formulations like herbal lip balms, herbal lipsticks, herbal creams, herbal shampoos, and herbal paste have always attracted considerable attention because of their good activity and comparatively lesser side-effects with synthetic materials. Herbal Cosmetics are defined as the beauty products which possess desirable physiological activity such as enhancing, soothing appearance, healing, conditioning properties because of herbal ingredients.

Along all cosmetic products, Natural lip balms preparation are most widely used to increase the beauty of lips and add glamour touch and shine to the beauty. Lip balms provide a natural way to promote healthy and moisturized lips. Current cosmetic lip products are based on use of toxic chemical ingredients with various adverse effect. That is why it leads to study natural ingredients used to production of natural lip balm.

Keywords:- Herbal lip balm, flavouring agent{orange powder}, Vitamin C.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's fastest growing civilization demand for natural products whose production is safe to the environment has increased the production of natural cosmetics. Lip balm is considered as the cosmetic product like lipstick which is used to prevent lips darkness and

protect against hazardous environmental factors. Natural lip balm preparations applied on the lips to avoid dryness and protect against adverse environmental pollutants that produce darkness to the lips. Natural lip balm helps to maintain and promote healthy lips. Vitamin C is mainly associated with the prevention of seasonal infections. This organic compound is a component of tablets and dietary supplements that strengthen immunity and improve the body's ability to absorb iron. Of course, these are not the only applications of vitamin C! The cosmetics of the twenty-first century are also based on its beneficial properties.¹⁻⁷

The main ingredients of lip balm: -

- Bees wax
- Castor oil
- Cocoa butter
- Vaseline
- Beet root powder
- Vitamin C
- Orange powder

These ingredients provide consistency and work as emollients in the formulation.⁸⁻¹²

II. ANATOMY OF LIPS

The lips play a role as organs which are designed for grazing, suction and speech. It is a combination of the skin, superficial facial, orbicularis muscle and muscles inserted around it. The margin of lips is covered with dry, red mucous membrane, continuous with the skin. The areolar tissue or submucous layer contains the coronary vessels which completely encircle the buccal orifice near the free margin of lips.

Fig. 1: Anatomy of lips

III. METHOD

- Weigh the required quantity of all ingredients {except beetroot powder, orange powder, vitamin C and mix in geometric proportion in porcelain dish.
- Place in water bath for double heating till it melts completely. After add beetroot powder, orange powder, vitamin C and stir continuously to mix it well.

- Pour the mixture into mould which is already lubricated with castor oil and let overflow the mixture.
- Place filled moulds in ice bath or freezer. Remove the mould and place the formulation in the container.
- Perform physical parameter, softening temp test, soothing effect etc.¹³⁻¹⁷

Table 1: Formulation table of herbal lip balm

Sr. no.	Ingredients	Formula F1	Formula F2
1	Bees wax	5 gm	5 gm
2	Cocoa butter	5 gm	5 gm
3	Castor oil	2 ml	1 ml
4	Vaseline	1 gm	1 gm
5	Beetroot powder	1 gm	0.5 gm
6	Orange peel powder	0.5 gm	0.5 gm
7	Vitamin C	0.02 gm	0.02 gm

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In the last few decades, there has been a tremendous boost in the use of cosmetics by women. However, the hazards caused by these chemicals have come into the limelight very recently. Consumers can take safe and effective advantage of herbal lip balms after thorough clinical trials. Compared to other beauty products, natural cosmetics are safe to use. Synthetic colouring agents may cause allergic reactions and be found to be carcinogenic.

The ability to desire the right cosmetics for you depends on accurate ingredient knowledge, body Prakriti assessment, personal needs, customer perception about the product, and benchmark product. Quality control for the ability and safety of herbal cosmetic products is of predominant importance. So quality control tests must be carried out for herbal cosmetics. It is assumed to be safe for longer periods. As per result F1 and F2 evaluate test very good result.

A. Result of Herbal Lip Balm:

Table 2: Physical parameter of herbal lip balm

Sr. no.	Parameter	F1	F2
1	Colour	Purple	Purple
2	Odour	Pleasant	Pleasant
3	Texture	Smooth	Smooth
4	Smoothing effect / greasy	Very smooth / greasy	Very smooth
5	pH	5.6	5.6

V. CONCLUSION

The herbal lipstick behavior of F1 and F2 was determined by in various evaluation test was made to identify the properties of lipsticks.

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